

Power quality improvement in grid connected hybrid renewable energy system using UPQC

Manpreet Singh, Lakhwinder Singh

Department of Electrical Engineering, Baba Banda Singh Bahadur Engineering College, IK Gujral Punjab Technical University, Jalandhar, India

Article Info

Article history:

Received Nov 21, 2024

Revised Apr 12, 2025

Accepted May 6, 2025

Keywords:

D-FACTS

Power quality

Renewable energy sources

Total harmonic distortion

Unified power quality

conditioner

ABSTRACT

The detection and mitigation of power quality issues have become essential due to the increased interest in integrating renewable energy sources to the power system. There are various methods to mitigate the power quality issues that arise due to the integration of composite renewable sources into the current power system. Distribution flexible alternating current transmission system (D-FACTS) devices are widely used for this purpose. Unified power quality conditioner (UPQC), due to its superior performance over other conditioners, has been used in the proposed system. The primary objective of this paper is to implement the UPQC to enhance power quality in grid-integrated photovoltaic-wind system by reducing total harmonic distortion (THD). MATLAB Simulink is utilized to verify the results of the proposed system. Total harmonic distortion analysis for a grid-connected photovoltaic-wind system without and with UPQC is compared. The efficacy of UPQC in reducing THD in a grid-integrated photovoltaic-wind system is presented. THD decreases from 24.06% to 11.19% when UPQC is linked to the proposed system. To validate the implementation of the proposed system, the results are compared with already published work.

This is an open access article under the [CC BY-SA](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-sa/4.0/) license.

Corresponding Author:

Manpreet Singh

Department of Electrical Engineering, Baba Banda Singh Bahadur Engineering College

IK Gujral Punjab Technical University

Jalandhar, Punjab, India

Email: mnprtsingh95@gmail.com

1. INTRODUCTION

Increasing worries about the exhaustion of fossil fuels and their effects on climate change have amplified the significance of renewable energy sources. Photovoltaic and wind are the top two green energy sources in use. All these sources of renewable electricity are very volatile due to their dependency on external factors such as sunlight and wind [1]. Although renewable energy sources are currently crucial components of electricity networks, there are persistent challenges with their integration, especially discrepancies between generation capacity and load demand [2]. Despite the power quality (PQ) problems caused by these integrations, grid-interconnection of renewable energy sources is need of hours [3]. In recent years, renewable energy has started to spread to almost all countries. Switching over to renewable energy sources because of distributed generation (DG), discarding the traditional energy sources due to their insufficiencies in the form of environmental degradation, fossil fuel exhaustion, non-flexibility, ageing, and also very low energy efficiency. Based on the trends, the majority of wind and solar hybrid generating systems will meet future energy requirements [4].

In the coming decades, half of the world's energy needs will be satisfied by renewable sources. Because wind and photovoltaic systems rely on nature, their power inputs vary greatly as well. The PQ

improvement in the ac-bus and constant power at the DC-link are significant problems [5]. Several distribution flexible alternating current transmission system (D-FACTS) devices with suitable control algorithms have been implemented to alleviate these PQ problems. By accurately adjusting a number of factors, including active and reactive power, impedances, and the voltage at the point of common coupling (PCC), these D-FACTS devices can enhance the dynamic behavior and dependability of the system [6], [7]. While examining the smart grid, the primary criterion is power quality, because of some active correction and quick filtration. Active power filters are therefore mostly chosen to compensate for power quality issues. Reduced power factor, high total harmonic distortion (THD) level, and power unbalance are some of the variables that must be taken into account while addressing the power quality problems. The voltage adjustment at the DC-link capacitor is crucial for achieving the optimal efficiency on a unified power quality conditioner (UPQC) [8].

Harmonics produced during the working of an induction furnace under non-linear variable load have been mitigated using UPQC and distributed static compensator (DSTATCOM) by Saggu *et al.* [9], [10]. Grid integration of renewable energy sources introduces power quality issues in the system. The implementation of DSTATCOM for improving power quality in grid-integrated wind energy systems has been proposed by Hussain *et al.* [11]. Malik *et al.* [12] implemented three-level inverters for the improvement of power quality in a hybrid photovoltaic-wind energy system. Poongothai *et al.* [13] proposed UPQC to enhance the power quality problems in grid-integrated solar power systems. Further, the power quality improvement in grid-connected solar-wind system employing genetic-based ANFIS controller is presented by Sree and Ankarao [14]. Mishra *et al.* [15] implemented the grid-connected PV system with a lymphoblastoid cell line filter for reducing power quality issues. Chapala *et al.* [16] mitigated the power quality issues in a solar-battery connected UPQC grid-integrated system. Further, power quality improvement in a grid-integrated PV system by using a series filter is presented by Hadi *et al.* [17]. The number of research papers has already been published on UPQC to improve the power quality in different kinds of systems, such as grid-connected PV systems or grid-connected wind systems alone. Considering the research gap in the reviewed literature, this paper presents the implementation of UPQC in the grid-connected hybrid photovoltaic-wind system to improve the THD level.

2. STRUCTURE OF UNIFIED POWER QUALITY CONDITIONER

A device called a UPQC fixes problems with voltage and current to enhance power quality [18]. Compensation for PQ problems with source voltage and load current is the main function of a UPQC [19]. In industrial power distribution systems, the UPQC can improve PQ at the PCC [20]. Series and shunt active power filters (APF) are combined to create UPQC. Shunt APF reduces distortions based on current, whereas series APF reduces distortions based on voltage [21]. The main components of UPQC are:

- (i) Voltage source inverters (VSI), both shunt and series [22]. Through its series connection with the line, the VSI structure functions as a voltage source [23]. However, by connecting it in parallel with the load, the shunt VSI structure serves as a source of current;
- (ii) Shunt inductor acts as the shunt inverter's network link; and
- (iii) To establish a common DC link, a capacitor is used. By connecting the two inverters, a capacitor maintains a constant and self-sustaining DC bus voltage across them.

The transformer links a series converter in the network [24]. Figure 1 shows the block diagram of UPQC.

Figure 1. Block diagram of UPQC

3. WORKING OF UNIFIED POWER QUALITY CONDITIONER

The UPQC combines two converters that operate as active power filters in series and shunt, sharing a DC capacitor. When the load demands it, a shunt-connected active power filter can inject reactive current to adjust the power factor, harmonic current to rectify load current harmonics, and negative and zero-sequence components to balance supply currents. It has the capability to control the DC bus voltage. To compensate

for the voltages in the source, a series active power filter injects negative and zero sequence voltages at the load bus. It also injects the required active power components to control the magnitude of load voltage and isolates the load bus from source voltage harmonics by injecting harmonic voltage [25].

4. MODELS OF PROPOSED GRID-CONNECTED HYBRID RENEWABLE ENERGY SYSTEM

The UPQC and the whole hybrid system are implemented in MATLAB/Simulink. To assess how well the UPQC performs in reducing power quality problems, two scenarios are simulated: (i) a grid-connected hybrid renewable energy system without UPQC and (ii) a grid-connected hybrid renewable energy system with UPQC. To ascertain the THD values, the proposed grid-connected hybrid renewable energy distributed system has been modelled both with and without UPQC. In order to feed power into the grid, an integrated PV-wind system has been used. A boost converter is then utilized to maintain DC voltages. Moreover, an inverter is used to transform DC input into AC so that it may be sent to the grid. The Simulink models of the grid-connected hybrid PV-wind system without UPQC and with UPQC are shown in Figures 2 and 3, respectively. The internal structure or subsystems of UPQC are depicted in Figures 4 and 5. Simulation parameters used for the proposed system are given in Table 1 [26].

Table 1. Simulation parameters

Sr. No.	Description	Parameters	Values
1.	Wind Turbine	Base torque (Nm)	8000
		Mechanical output power (kW)	75
		The base-power-electrical generator (kW/pf)	75/0.9
		Base speed of wind (m/s)	10
2.	Photovoltaic	Irradiance	950
		Real power generated (kW)	30
3.	Connected Grid	System phase voltage (V)	440
		System frequency (Hz)	50
4.	Non-linear Load	Nominal system voltage (V)	440

Figure 2. Simulink model of a grid-connected hybrid renewable energy system without UPQC

Figure 3. Simulink model of grid-connected hybrid renewable energy system with UPQC

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

The authors are indebted to the I.K.G. Punjab Technical University Jalandhar, Kapurthala for providing the advanced research facilities for this research work.

FUNDING INFORMATION

Authors state no funding involved.

AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS STATEMENT

This journal uses the Contributor Roles Taxonomy (CRediT) to recognize individual author contributions, reduce authorship disputes, and facilitate collaboration.

Name of Author	C	M	So	Va	Fo	I	R	D	O	E	Vi	Su	P	Fu
Manpreet Singh	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓			✓	✓				
Lakhwinder Singh		✓			✓	✓			✓	✓	✓	✓		

C : Conceptualization

M : Methodology

So : Software

Va : Validation

Fo : Formal analysis

I : Investigation

R : Resources

D : Data Curation

O : Writing - Original Draft

E : Writing - Review & Editing

Vi : Visualization

Su : Supervision

P : Project administration

Fu : Funding acquisition

CONFLICT OF INTEREST STATEMENT

The authors have no conflicts of interest to declare.

DATA AVAILABILITY

Data availability is not applicable to this paper as no new data were created or analyzed in this study.

REFERENCES

- [1] R. Venkatesan, C. Kumar, C. R. Balamurugan, and T. Senjyu, "Enhancing power quality in grid-connected hybrid renewable energy systems using UPQC and optimized O-FOPID," *Frontiers in Energy Research*, vol. 12, 2024, doi: 10.3389/fenrg.2024.1425412.
- [2] A. H. A. Elkasem, S. Kamel, M. Khamies, and L. Nasrat, "Frequency regulation in a hybrid renewable power grid: an effective strategy utilizing load frequency control and redox flow batteries," *Scientific Reports*, vol. 14, no. 1, 2024, doi: 10.1038/s41598-024-58189-2.
- [3] A. Ranjan and J. Choudhary, "Power quality enhancement in grid-connected energy system with UPQC using hybrid PSO-GWO optimization technique," *Lecture Notes in Networks and Systems*, vol. 890, pp. 23–37, 2024, doi: 10.1007/978-981-99-9531-8_3.
- [4] S. Choudhury and G. K. Sahoo, "A critical analysis of different power quality improvement techniques in microgrid," *e-Prime - Advances in Electrical Engineering, Electronics and Energy*, vol. 8, 2024, doi: 10.1016/j.prime.2024.100520.
- [5] P. K. Pandey, R. Kumar, V. Gupta, A. Kanungo, and S. Diwania, "An innovative hybrid controller-based combined grid-connected hybrid renewable energy system," *Electrical Engineering*, 2024, doi: 10.1007/s00202-024-02363-2.
- [6] K. Jha and A. G. Shaik, "A comprehensive review of power quality mitigation in the scenario of solar PV integration into utility grid," *e-Prime - Advances in Electrical Engineering, Electronics and Energy*, vol. 3, 2023, doi: 10.1016/j.prime.2022.100103.
- [7] B. H. Alajrash, M. Salem, M. Swadi, T. Senjyu, M. Kamarol, and S. Motahhir, "A comprehensive review of FACTS devices in modern power systems: Addressing power quality, optimal placement, and stability with renewable energy penetration," *Energy Reports*, vol. 11, pp. 5350–5371, 2024, doi: 10.1016/j.egy.2024.05.011.
- [8] T. Arulkumar and N. Chandrasekaran, "Development of improved sparrow search-based PI controller for power quality enhancement using UPQC integrated with medical devices," *Engineering Applications of Artificial Intelligence*, vol. 116, 2022, doi: 10.1016/j.engappai.2022.105444.
- [9] T. S. Saggi, L. Singh, B. Gill, and O. P. Malik, "Effectiveness of UPQC in mitigating harmonics generated by an induction furnace," *Electric Power Components and Systems*, vol. 46, no. 6, pp. 629–636, 2018, doi: 10.1080/15325008.2018.1460641.
- [10] T. S. Saggi, L. Singh, and B. Gill, "Harmonics mitigation in a steel industry using 11-level cascaded multilevel inverter-based DSTATCOM," *Canadian Journal of Electrical and Computer Engineering*, vol. 40, no. 2, 2017, doi: 10.1109/CJECE.2017.2681686.
- [11] J. Hussain, M. Hussain, S. Raza, and M. Siddique, "Power quality improvement of grid connected wind energy system using DSTATCOM-BESS," *International Journal of Renewable Energy Research*, vol. 9, no. 3, 2019, doi: 10.20508/ijrer.v9i3.9802.g7717.
- [12] M. Malik and P. R. Sharma, "Power quality improvement in hybrid photovoltaic and wind power system using 3 levels inverter," *Proceedings - 2020 International Conference on Advances in Computing, Communication and Materials, ICACCM 2020*, pp. 253–260, 2020, doi: 10.1109/ICACCM50413.2020.9212821.
- [13] S. Poongothai and S. Srinath, "Power quality enhancement in solar power with grid connected system using UPQC," *Microprocessors and Microsystems*, vol. 79, 2020, doi: 10.1016/j.micpro.2020.103300.
- [14] V. S. Sree and M. Ankarao, "Power quality enhancement of solar-wind grid connected system employing genetic-based ANFIS controller," *Paladyn*, vol. 14, no. 1, 2023, doi: 10.1515/pjbr-2022-0116.

- [15] D. P. Mishra, K. K. Rout, S. Mishra, M. Nivas, R. K. P. R. Naidu, and S. R. Salkuti, "Power quality enhancement of grid-connected PV system," *International Journal of Power Electronics and Drive Systems*, vol. 14, no. 1, pp. 369–377, 2023, doi: 10.11591/ijpeds.v14.i1.pp369-377.
- [16] S. Chapala, R. L. Narasimham, and T. R. Das, "Power Quality Enhancement in Solar PV and Battery Integrated UPQC grid connected system," *International Journal of Electrical and Electronics Research*, vol. 11, no. 2, pp. 291–298, 2023, doi: 10.37391/IJEER.110207.
- [17] H. A. Hadi, A. Kassem, H. Amoud, and S. Nadweh, "Improve power quality and stability of grid - connected PV system by using series filter," *Heliyon*, vol. 10, no. 21, 2024, doi: 10.1016/j.heliyon.2024.e39757.
- [18] S. Baswaraju *et al.*, "Study on UPQC integration benefits in a hybrid solar wind energy system," *E3S Web of Conferences*, vol. 552, 2024, doi: 10.1051/e3sconf/202455201139.
- [19] A. S. Vigneshwar, A. Shunmugalatha, and A. Madhan, "power quality enhancement in hybrid sustainable energy systems grid-connected scheme by modified non-dominated sorting genetic algorithm," *Journal of Electrical Engineering and Technology*, vol. 19, no. 4, pp. 2029–2046, 2024, doi: 10.1007/s42835-023-01676-9.
- [20] A. Alhatim, F. Tahir, and A. N. Alsammak, "Optimization of power quality using the unified power quality conditioner (UPQC) with unbalanced loads," *Al-Rafidain Engineering Journal (AREJ)*, vol. 27, no. 2, pp. 101–109, 2022, doi: 10.33899/rengj.2022.133962.1175.
- [21] T. Palanisamy and G. S. Thangamuthu, "Optimal power quality improvement in distribution system with UPQC using an improved strategy," *Optimal Control Applications and Methods*, vol. 45, no. 4, pp. 1433–1455, 2024, doi: 10.1002/oca.3105.
- [22] D. R. Mani, S. Muthu, and K. Kasilingam, "Enhanced power quality and efficient photovoltaic integration with a PV-based unified power quality conditioner using optimized MPPT technique," *Electrical Engineering*, 2024, doi: 10.1007/s00202-024-02627-x.
- [23] H. Manoharan, S. Karuppannan, K. Chandrasekaran, and S. Barua, "Power quality improvement of grid-connected solar power plant systems using a novel fractional order proportional integral derivative controller technique," *IET Renewable Power Generation*, 2024, doi: 10.1049/rpg2.13128.
- [24] A. Y. Qasim, F. R. Tahir, and A. N. B. Alsammak, "improving power quality in distribution systems using UPQC: An overview," *Journal Europeen des Systemes Automatisés*, vol. 57, no. 2, pp. 311–322, 2024, doi: 10.18280/jesa.570201.
- [25] A. Y. Qasim, F. R. Tahir, and A. N. B. Alsammak, "Voltage sag, voltage swell and harmonics reduction using unified power quality conditioner (UPQC) under nonlinear loads," *Iraqi Journal for Electrical and Electronic Engineering*, vol. 17, no. 2, pp. 140–150, 2021, doi: 10.37917/ijeee.17.2.16.
- [26] B. S. Goud and B. L. Rao, "Power quality enhancement in grid-connected PV/wind/battery using UPQC: Atom search optimization," *Journal of Electrical Engineering & Technology*, vol. 16, no. 2, pp. 821–835, Mar. 2021, doi: 10.1007/s42835-020-00644-x.

APPENDIX

Figure 6. THD measurements of a grid-connected hybrid renewable energy system without UPQC

Figure 7. Load voltage and current waveforms (magnitude versus time) for a grid-connected hybrid renewable energy system without UPQC

Figure 8. THD measurements of grid-connected hybrid renewable energy system with UPQC

Figure 9. Load voltage and current waveforms (magnitude versus time) of grid-connected hybrid renewable energy system with UPQC

BIOGRAPHIES OF AUTHORS

Manpreet Singh is working as an Assistant Professor in Electrical Engineering at Baba Banda Singh Bahadur Engineering College, Fatehgarh Sahib, Punjab, India. He obtained his B.Tech. (Electrical) in 2006 from Baba Banda Singh Bahadur Engineering College, Fatehgarh Sahib, and M.Tech. (Electrical Engineering) in 2013 from Guru Nanak Dev Engineering College, Ludhiana. His research interests include energy management, power quality improvement, smart grids, and renewable energy systems. He can be contacted at email: mnprtsingh95@gmail.com.

Dr. Lakhwinder Singh is working as the Dean of Academics and Professor in Electrical Engineering at Baba Banda Singh Bahadur Engineering College, Fatehgarh Sahib, Punjab, India. He obtained his B.E. (Electrical) in 1990 from Guru Nanak Dev Engineering College, Ludhiana, M.E. (Power Systems) in 1995 from Punjab University, Chandigarh, and Ph.D. in 2009 from Punjab Technical University, Jalandhar. He is a member of IEEE, a life member of the Indian Society for Technical Education, and a fellow of the Institution of Engineers (India). He is the author of 72 technical papers published in national and international journals/conferences. His research interests include fuzzy logic, optimization techniques, power system operation and control, power quality improvement, smart grids, and renewable energy systems. He can be contacted at email: b_lakh@yahoo.com.